

Decentralised Financial Investment Platform for Energy Companies

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Abstract

Blockchain Technology is a disruptive innovation in the technology landscape and every industry is exploring various use cases of using BlockChain technology. In this process we have developed a “Decentralised Financial Investment Platform for Energy Companies” using open source Ethereum Blockchain. The application is completely autonomous based on “Smart Contracts”. Investors can invest in our platform through Smart Contracts. Fund raiser can create their projects using smart contracts. All the earnings from a specific project will be distributed among the investors automatically based on the “Smart Contracts”. It is a unique concept developed on Etehreum Blockchain and Smart Contracts for Energy Companies.

Keywords:

Author biography

Srinivasa Raju Vuppalapati Srinivasa Raju Vuppalapati having Masters in Computer Science from JNTU,Kakinada has got 16+ years of experience in Academia / Industry.A passionate engineer who can acquire new technologies at a very faster rate. The core areas in which he is interested and working on are Blockchain Technologies, Artificial Intelligence, Web Development, Semantic Web,A Certified Ethical Hacker from EC Council, U.S.A.

Rao Dronamraju Rao Dronamraju has more than 30 years of experience and accomplishments in Fortune 100 and Startup Companies in US and Canada.He has broad and deep expertise in diverse enterprise computing technologies including Blockchain/Bitcoin,IT/Cyber Security, Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Containers, Converged/Infrastructure Technologies with special focus on Financial Services & Healthcare Industry Applications.

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